

FUTURE CHALLENGES AND INDUSTRIAL ADOPTION STRATEGIES FOR STRUCTURAL SUPERCAPACITORS

E. S. Greenhalgh^{1*}, M. S. P. Shaffer², A. Kucernak², D. B. Anthony^{1,2}, E. Senokos², S. Nguyen¹, F. Pernice¹, G. Zhang², G. Qi¹, K. Balaskandan^{1,2}, M Valkova^{1,2}.

¹ Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London, UK

² Department of Chemistry, Imperial College London, UK

* Corresponding author (e.greenhalgh@imperial.ac.uk)

Imperial College London, UK

www.imperial.ac.uk/composites-centre/

August 2019

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Introduction and Motivation

Going beyond Smart Materials....

- Conventional *reductionalist* design approach - maximise efficiency of individual subcomponents.
 - ⇒ Difficult compromises;
 - ⇒ Limiting technological advance and stifling innovative design.
- Different *holistic* approach; structures and materials which simultaneously perform more than one function.

Smart (Multifunctional Structures)...

Implanting of secondary materials or devices within a parent laminate to imbue additional functionality...

⇒ e.g. embedding devices within structural materials

Multifunctional Materials....

Constituents synergistically and holistically perform two very different roles....

⇒ e.g. a nanostructured carbon lattice carrying mechanical load whilst intercalating lithium ions for electrical energy storage

J. P. Thomas & M. A. Qidwai, JOM. v57 p18-24. 2005.

Jacques E., et.al, Electrochemistry Communications, Volume 35, 2013, Pages 65-67.

Motivation for Multifunctional Materials

- We can now tailor composite properties beyond purely the mechanical perspective.
 - ⇒ New and diverse functionalities being added.
- Multifunctional composite materials has potential to revolutionize transportation, portable electronics and infrastructure.
- Focus of this paper is structural supercapacitors:
 - ⇒ Carry mechanical loads whilst storing and delivering electrical energy.
- **Objectives:**
 - ⇒ Overview of the structural supercapacitor research at Imperial College London;
 - ⇒ Outline the near and medium-term challenges for these new materials;
 - ⇒ Suggest industrial adoption strategies.

The car's body panels serve as a battery

Multifunctional structural power concept (Volvo Cars)

Multifunctional demonstrator from STORAGE project

Motivation – Example (E-Fan)

E-Fan 1.0 (500kg)

Structure/Systems (333kg)

What electrical performance of the Structural Power Composite (SPC) is required to exceed the performance (i.e. 60 min endurance) of the conventional system (i.e. load-bearing structure + batteries)?

Scenario	Aircraft Mass (kg)	Specific Energy (Wh/kg)	Specific Power (W/kg)
Remove battery , SPC to provide energy <i>(i.e. reduce aircraft weight).</i>	333	87	310
Remove battery, replace with SPC <i>(i.e. aircraft weight maintained)</i>	500	71	179

Structural Supercapacitors – Imperial College Research

Supercapacitor Device

Conventional Supercapacitor

Structural Supercapacitor

Research Streams

Reinforcement Development

Carbon aerogels possess much higher specific surface areas compared to carbon fibres.

Also high stiffness which is beneficial to the mechanical performance:

- Active materials for electric double layer capacitors
- Scaffold/current collectors for redox active materials: reducing dead weight

CAG coating of CFs and detailed microstructure

Structural Electrolyte Development

Aspirational multifunctional electrolyte:

- Ionic conductivity – 1 mS/cm;
- Young's Modulus – 1 GPa.

Form a bicontinuous structure with one phase responsible for providing mechanical strength while another ensures ionic conductivity.

Device Fabrication and Assembly

- (a) Infuse individual CF lamina with CAG precursor;
- (b) Pyrolyse individual lamina to form the CF/CAG;
- (c) Wash CF/CAG lamina;
- (d) Assemble device to produce CF/Sep/CF laminate;
- (e) Infuse laminate with multifunctional matrix & cure.

Summary of semi-structural & MF cell performance

Electrodes	Separator	Electrolyte	C (F)	m (g)	V (V)	ESR (Ω)	C* (F/g)	E* (Wh/kg)	P* (kW/kg)
CAG CF 43 gsm	Woven GF (242 μ m)	EMI-TFSI	0.68	0.91	2.7	2.66	0.8	0.8	0.8
CAG CF 43 gsm	PET/ceramic (23 μm)	EMI-TFSI	1.01	0.36	2.7	1.49	3.1	3.2	3.4
CAG CF 43 gsm	Woven GF (50 μ m)	MF (40%)	0.34	0.39	2.7	7.45	0.9	0.9	0.6
CAG CF 43 gsm	PET/ceramic (23 μm)	MF (40%)	0.51	0.36	2.7	4.80	1.4	1.4	1.1
<i>Maxwell BCAP0150¹, length = 50 mm, dia. = 25 mm</i>			<i>150</i>	<i>32</i>	<i>2.7</i>	<i>14 mΩ</i>	<i>4.7</i>	4.7	4.1

Conventional supercapacitor
 $\Gamma=4.7\text{Wh/kg}$ & $P=4.1\text{kW/kg}$

*Normalised to active mass

C carbon fabrics	138 mg
A erogel	62 mg
S eparator (PC)	53 mg
E lectrolyte	107 mg

Future Challenges

Future Challenges – Multifunctional Design

- Conventional design approach
 - ⇒ Implement new properties and then characterize how the improved performance compares to that of the COTS (Current Off The Shelf) for the same function.
- However, structural power material cannot...
 - ⇒ Offer better mechanical load-carrying capability than a fully optimized conventional structural material
 - ⇒ Offer better electrochemical performance than a conventional battery or supercapacitor.
- ***Taking a holistic view during design is vital***
 - ⇒ Structural power materials partially undertake the role of both the structural components (e.g. spars or skins) and the energy storage (e.g. battery, supercapacitor, etc.);
 - ⇒ Hence a system approach to design, rather than the conventional compartmentalized approach, should be followed.
- Structural Power Materials also offer
 - ⇒ Localization of power sources (i.e. reducing wiring)
 - ⇒ Opportunities to tailor mass distribution across a platform.
- **Need to capture this within a new design methodology**

Future Challenges – Scale-Up and Fabrication

- Fabrication methodologies for structural power materials very different to conventional approaches.
- Melding of polymer composite manufacture and electrochemical device fabrication.
 - ⇒ Any exposure of the matrix/electrolyte to ambient moisture is critical to electrochemical performance.
 - ⇒ ‘Moisture-free’ composite fabrication required
- Fabrication of curved components present additional challenges:
 - ⇒ Currently being addressed through the development of masking of fold lines/barriers, to permit monofunctional and multifunctional domains.
 - ⇒ Investigating as a route to achieve continuity of carbon-fibres across monofunctional/multifunctional boundaries.

Future Challenges - Encapsulation

- Critical near-term challenge is how to encapsulate the structural power material.
- Isolate from the surrounding systems, conventional structure, and ultimately the environment, whilst still transferring mechanical load across the monofunctional/multifunctional interfaces.
- Conventional energy storage devices are encased in inert, insulating sheaths.
- Electrolyte phase (Ionic liquid) is leached out by the uncured epoxy, leading to considerable loss of electrical performance.

*2 GF+ MTM57 B-staged
for 30 min, at 80°C*

Capacitance (60% drop) & ESR (90% rise)

Future Challenges – Certification & Predictive Modelling

- Most significant hurdle is that of certification, particularly for aerospace applications.
 - ⇒ Conventional structural materials are required to demonstrate airworthiness through the “Rouchon pyramid”.
- Structural power materials would not only have to be mechanically certified, but also electrochemically too.
 - ⇒ Any mechanical/electrochemical interactions (e.g. mechanical cycling inducing damage that reduces the electrical performance) needs to be considered.
- Best addressed through developing predictive modelling
 - ⇒ Development of finite element models which can predict both mechanical and electrochemical behavior, and any coupling interactions.

Future Challenges – Predictive Modelling Strategy

Consolidation modelling

Electrochemical Modelling

Mechanical Modelling

Multifunctional structural element

- Provide a framework to support certification of structural power devices
- Couple electrical and mechanical models

Future Challenges – In-service Conditions

- Range of in-service requirement and conditions to which structural power materials could be exposed, and would be required to tolerate.
- These include
 - ⇒ Cycling (both mechanical and electrical)
 - ⇒ Temperature extremes,
 - ⇒ Fire resistance
 - ⇒ Machining/Finishing
 - ⇒ Impact and Damage Tolerance.
 - ⇒ Inspection/Repair/Disposal

Local heating following penetrative impact

Cyclic performance

Drilling damage

Potential Adoption Routes

- Structural power is still a very immature technology.
- Performance is too low to replace existing propulsion (aerospace and automotive)
- More reasonable target is to replace auxiliary power sources, such as to reduce the electrical load on main power sources.
- Automotive
 - ⇒ Utilize in secondary sources (stop/start battery, etc);
 - ⇒ Focus on panels and non-safety critical applications.
- Aerospace
 - ⇒ Cabin applications (benign temperature regime);
 - ⇒ Powering seat-back personal displays, etc;
 - ⇒ Local power sources for safety equipment;
 - ⇒ Systems and electronics boxes.
- Other Sectors
 - ⇒ Electric bicycles – energy recovery, etc;
 - ⇒ Mobile electronics.

Volvo bootlid demonstrator from STORAGE project

Doorframe demonstrator from SORCERER

Conclusions

- Structural power composites is an exciting emerging technology for transportation and portable electronics.
- Current performance - *c.f.* conventional supercapacitor at device level (4.7Wh/kg & 4.1kW/kg)
 - ⇒ 3.2Wh/kg & 3.4kW/kg (*semi-structural*);
 - ⇒ 1.4Wh/kg & 1.1kW/kg (*structural*).
- Still considerable technical hurdles to be addressed, but the outlook is promising.
 - ⇒ *Multifunctional Design*
 - ⇒ *Scale-up and Fabrication*
 - ⇒ *Encapsulation*
 - ⇒ *Certification and Predictive Modelling*
 - ⇒ *In-service Conditions*
- Early adoption routes – auxiliary applications and power sources (aircraft cabin)
- My personal view – structural power, and the generic concept of truly multifunctional materials, is such a simple idea which will provide huge performance benefits and design freedom, it's clearly a case of **when** not **if** it is widely adopted.
- ***In 50 years time, we won't be using discrete monofunctional batteries, we will build structures from multifunctional materials with innate electrical energy storage.***

Acknowledgements

Acknowledge the funding provided by the EPSRC Future Composites Research Manufacturing Hub (EP/P006701/1), the EPSRC Beyond Structural project (EP/P007465/1), the European Office of Aerospace Research and Development (IOE Grant FA9550-17-1-0251) and EU Clean Sky 2 (SORCERER Project #738085).

- *Ex-researchers* - Habtom Asfaw, Guohui Zhang, & Kaan Bilge
- *Collaborators* - University of Durham, University of Bristol, KTH (Sweden), Chalmers (Sweden), IMDEA (Spain)

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